

Geophysical Research Letters

Supporting Information for

**Tropical plant species living under P limitation show
signs of greater resistance to drought**

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Introduction

This supplementary information contains 3 figures and 4 tables.

Figure S1: Percentage loss in hydraulic conductivity as a function of pressure for stems of 9 woody karst species in this study. The difference between $\Psi_{\min}$ (blue dash line) and P50 (pink dash line) is hydraulic safety margin. PLC curves were fitted using all data; Species abbreviations follow Table 1(code).

Figure S2: Phylogenetic relationships in this study.

Figure S3: Relationship between mass-based leaf P concentrations (P_{mass}) and leaf N concentrations (N_{mass}). Gray lines represent the N:P ratios of 14 and 16. Points above the N:P = 16 line indicate P limitation; points below the N:P = 14 line indicate N limitation.

Table S2: The soil total nitrogen and phosphorus in 10-20 cm depth

species	Total nitrogen(g/kg)	Total phosphorus (g/kg)
Eu	2.75	0.42
Cb	3.34	0.67
Pp	2.81	0.27
Ts	4.36	0.73
Qf	4.38	0.43
Ks	5.20	0.31
Pa	4.65	0.37
Ps	4.36	0.71
Pl	5.70	0.59

Table S3 Characteristics of the nine woody species tested in the field study.

Species	Family	Code	Canopy height (m)
<i>Eucommia ulmoides</i>	Eucommiaceae	Eu	5–6
<i>Pyrus pyrifolia</i>	Rosaceae	Pp	5–6
<i>Catalpa bungei</i>	Bignoniaceae	Cb	8–9
<i>Toona sinensis</i>	Meliaceae	Ts	11–13
<i>Quercus fabri</i>	Fagaceae	Qf	9–10
<i>Populus adenopoda</i>	Salicaceae	Pa	10–13
<i>Kalopanax septemlobus</i>	Araliaceae	Ks	11–12
<i>Platycarya strobilacea</i>	Juglandaceae	Ps	7–8
<i>Platycarya longipes</i>	Juglandaceae	Pl	5–6

Supplementary Table 4 Characteristics of measured leaf and stem traits from detailed experiments.

Parameter	Abbreviation	Unit	Average value	Standard error	Minvalue	Max value
Leaf nitrogen / phosphorus ratio	N:P	None	20.21	2.31	9.67	30.56
Predawn leaf water potential	Ψ_{predawn}	MPa	-0.16	0.01	-0.23	-0.11
Min leaf water potential	Ψ_{min}	MPa	-2.24	0.10	-2.68	-1.82
Stomatal conductance	gs	$\text{mmol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$	0.21	0.02	0.09	0.34
Specific conductivity of terminal stems	Ks	$\text{Kg m}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1} \text{MPa}^{-1}$	5.26	0.62	2.89	8.11
Xylem water potential at 50% loss of hydraulic conductivity	P50	MPa	-2.12	0.13	-2.61	-1.41
Wood density	WD	g cm^{-3}	0.55	0.01	0.49	0.64
Hydraulic safety margin	SM	MPa	-0.12	0.20	-0.81	0.76
Huber value	HV	$\times 10^{-4}$	1.07	0.19	0.35	2.91
Vessel wall thickness	t	μm	2.20	0.30	0.74	3.43
Vessel wall reinforcement	t/b	$\mu\text{m } \mu\text{m}^{-1}$	0.08	0.004	0.06	0.11